

Title: Optimising HIV Case Identification in Low-Yield Settings: Evidence from Routine Programme Data in Kebbi, Sokoto, and Zamfara States, Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Progress toward the UNAIDS 95-95-95 targets depends not only on HIV testing coverage but also on the efficiency of case identification. In settings with low testing yield, high testing volumes with declining positivity can reduce programme efficiency and slow progress toward the First 95. This analysis assessed HIV testing performance and predictors of HIV positivity using routine programme data from Kebbi, Sokoto, and Zamfara States in FY25 (October 2024 to September 2025).

Methods: A retrospective analysis of routinely collected HIV testing services (HTS) data was conducted using cleaned individual-level testing records, with facility-level summaries used to describe testing volume and yield patterns across sites. Analyses were stratified by sex, age group, priority subpopulations (including pregnant/breastfeeding women and adolescents and young people), testing modality, location, and fiscal quarter. HIV yield was defined as the proportion of positive tests among all tests conducted. Multivariable logistic regression was used to identify independent predictors of HIV positivity.

Results: A total of 370,673 HIV tests were conducted across the three states, with an overall positivity yield of 0.64%. Despite high testing volume, overall yield remained below 1%, highlighting opportunities to improve efficiency through more targeted approaches. HIV positivity increased with age, with adults aged ≥ 25 years having higher odds of testing positive compared with adolescents aged 15–24 years (OR=2.29; 95% CI: 2.02–2.62), while children aged 10–14 years had lower odds (OR=0.35; 95% CI: 0.22–0.54). Compared with routine provider-initiated testing (PITC) as the reference group, index testing demonstrated the highest yield (4.11%) and was associated with substantially higher odds of HIV positivity (OR = 7.99; 95% CI: 5.44–11.97). VCT also showed higher odds of HIV positivity (OR=2.38; 95% CI: 1.71–3.40), while PMTCT and paediatric testing modalities consistently demonstrated lower yields (OR<0.20). Male clients had lower odds of HIV positivity than females (OR=0.46; 95% CI: 0.41–0.51). Significant geographic variation was observed, with substantially higher odds of HIV positivity in Kebbi State (OR = 40.49; 95% CI: 26.08–61.68) and lower odds in Sokoto State (OR = 0.62; 95% CI: 0.54–0.71). Testing yield declined across the year, with lower odds of positivity in Q3 (OR=0.61; 95% CI: 0.53–0.70) and Q4 (OR=0.77; 95% CI: 0.67–0.90) relative to Q1. Differences in yield across modalities likely reflect variations in targeting and client risk profiles across service delivery entry points.

Conclusion: Routine programme data from Kebbi, Sokoto, and Zamfara States show a clear misalignment between HIV testing volume and case identification yield. Scaling up higher-yield modalities such as index testing, alongside targeted testing approaches, while maintaining essential PMTCT and paediatric testing services, is critical for improving efficiency and

accelerating progress toward the First 95 in resource-constrained settings. Testing efficiency was lower among adolescents and young people than among older adults, highlighting the need for adolescent-responsive strategies to strengthen case identification in this group.

Keywords: HIV Testing Services, UNAIDS 95-95-95 Targets, Case Finding, Positivity Yield, Routine Programme Data, Nigeria